

Assessment of ground water pollution using multivariate statistical techniques in and around Municipal Solid Waste dumpsite : A case study from Autonagar, Hyderabad, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract : Application of different multivariate statistical approaches for the interpretation of data during monitoring of groundwater near the MSW dumpsite in Autonagar area, Hyderabad is presented in this study. A number of physico-chemical characteristics of groundwater sample around the dumpsite were analyzed so as to ascertain the extent of ground water pollution by leachates from MSW. Data set thus obtained was treated using R-Mode Factor Analysis (FA) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using IBM SPSS20 Statistics Software. FA identified three factors responsible for data structure explaining 65.4% of total variance and was compared with the Bureau of Indian Standards for drinking water. This allowed grouping of selected parameter according to common features and leading to the explanation of geogenic pollution.

Keywords : Municipal solid waste (MSW) dumpsite, groundwater, multivariate analysis, factor analysis.

Introduction

The composition of ground water is dependent on natural factors (geological, topographical, meteorological, hydrological and biological) in the drainage basin and varies with the run off volumes, weather conditions and water levels. The effects of human activities on water quality are both widespread and varied in the degree to which they disrupt the ecosystem and/or restrict water use¹. It is reported that ground water contamination is increasing due to anthropogenic activities like disposal of domestic waste². Landfills/Municipal solid waste dumpsites have been identified as one of the major threats to ground water resources³.

When rain percolates through the solid waste and reacts with the products of decomposition, chemicals and other materials in the waste, a thick liquid known as leachate is formed. The leachate is anoxic, acidic and

rich in inorganic acid groups, sulphate ions and with high concentration of metal ions. Leachates from solid waste sites are known to seep slowly through the layers of soil beneath and contaminate the ground water sources deep down⁴. The urban and suburban population in and around Hyderabad city greatly depend on ground water from weathered and fractured Precambrian bedrock for various purposes other than drinking⁵.

The dissolved physico-chemical parameters in ground water play a significant role in classifying and assessing water quality⁶. Water in soil moves from point where it has relatively high energy status to points where its energy status is lower. The first factor is the elevation position in the soil relative to the reference level. The higher an object is located above the reference level, the higher is its gravitational energy. This is true also of any given quantity of water in soil; the higher the water is located

in the soil profile, the higher is its gravitational energy. Gravitational energy is expressed as the number of centimeters or inches above or below an arbitrarily chosen reference⁷. The extent of contamination of ground water quality due to leachate percolation depends upon a number of factors like leachate composition, rainfall, depth and distance of the well from the pollution source⁸.

The present study was taken up to establish the levels of dissolved major ions and metals in and around solid waste dumping site at Autonagar, Hyderabad, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Study area :

The Autonagar dumpsite in Hyderabad is spread over an area of 47 acres and used to receive an average of 800 mt garbage per day. About 8.7 lakhs m³ MSW has been dumped at this dumpsite, which weighs ~4.35 lakhs tonne. The Municipal Corporation of Hyderabad (MCH) stopped dumping of garbage at Autonagar site in 2005. In 2007 a composting marketing company signed a five year contract with MCH for bio-mining the entire 47 acre site, excavating the waste in vertical layers from a garbage cliff and using their own biocultures on aerobic windrows along with up to 25% of fresh garbage.

The study area (around the dumpsite) is covered by granite. The area is semi-arid with subtropical climate conditions. The temperature varies between 25 to 45 °C. It receives more than 80% precipitation from south-west monsoon with an average rainfall of 812 mm⁶.

The location of the Dumpsite is : Lt. 17°20'59.49" N; Lg. 78°34'48.16" E; Elevation (ground sea level) : 1688 ft.

Ground water samples were collected from the residential colonies situated around the dumpsite (Fig. 1) in the year 2008 pre-monsoon season. Altogether fifteen samples were collected. The area of sampling, its Topographical elevation at ground sea level (source www.google.com/earth) and its distance from the dumpsite is given below :

S₁ Deer Park (1735 ft, 1.7 km), S₂ Institute of Dry Land Agriculture (1677 ft, 1 km), S₃ Autonagar (1684 ft, 0.30 km), S₄ Sahara Estate (1684 ft, 1 km), S₅ Vivekananda Nagar (1729 ft, 1.66 km), S₆ Vijayasri Colony (1713 ft, 1.47 km), S₇ Local Park (1698 ft, 2.08

Fig. 1

km), S₈ Balaji Nagar (1698 ft, 2 km), S₉ SPS Residency (1700 ft, 1.68 km), S₁₀ Raja Rajeshwary Colony (1666 ft, 2.32 km), S₁₁ Himapuri Colony (1660 ft, 1.3 km), S₁₂ Southend Park (1652 ft, 1.2 km), S₁₃ Mansoorabad (1656 ft, 2.06 km), S₁₄ Tyagarayanagar (1608 ft, 2.09 km), S₁₅ Bandlaguda (1596 ft, 2.10 km), S₁₆ Chinna Pedda Cheruvu (1700 ft, 2.28 km).

Materials and methods :

Ground water samples were collected in post summer season from fifteen continually used bore wells (Depth 200 to 300 ft) located around dumpsite in 1 L polypropylene bottles, with in 3 km of horizontal distance from the MSW dumpsite.

TDS, pH and EC were measured using Elico pH/EC/TDS meter immediately at the sampling site. Sodium and potassium were determined by systronics flame photometer. Calcium, magnesium, carbonate and bicarbonate were estimated by titrimetric analysis. Chloride, sulphate, nitrate and phosphate were determined by using Dionex Ion-Chromatographer. Metals were analyzed by ICP-MS (Perkin-Elmer Sciex Elan DR C11)⁹.

Factor analysis :

Factor analysis is a multivariate statistical method that yields the general relationship between measured vari-

ables by showing multivariate patterns that may help to classify the original data. It also enables the distribution of the resulting factors to be determined¹⁰. Factor analysis is a very powerful technique applied to reduce the dimensionality of a dataset consisting of a large number of interrelated variables, while retaining as much as possible the variability presented in dataset and with a minimum loss of information¹¹. This reduction is achieved by transforming the dataset into a new set of variable factors, which are orthogonal (non-correlated) and are arranged in decreasing order of importance. FA can also be used to generate hypotheses regarding causal mechanisms or to screen variables for subsequent analysis.

Data processing :

Factor analysis is applied on experimental data standardized through z-scale transformation in order to avoid misclassification due to wide differences in data dimensionality¹². Furthermore, the standardization procedure eliminates the influence of different units of measurements and renders the data dimensionless. In the standardization, the raw data were converted to unit less form of zero mean and a variance of one, by subtracting from each variable the mean of data set and dividing by standard deviation. This type of ordination reduces the dimensionality of the data set and minimizes the loss of information caused by reduction. The first step of the analysis is to standardize the raw data. Let X_1, \dots, X_p denote P variables, each with N observations. The j -th observation of the i -th variable is X_{ij} , where $i = 1, \dots, P$ and $j = 1, \dots, N$, if x_m and S_i denote the mean and standard deviation, respectively, computed from the N observations of the i -th variable, then, the j -th observation of the i -th variable is expressed in standardized units as :

$$Z_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij} - x_m}{S}$$

where Z_{ij} is the j -th value of the standardized variable Z_i . The mean and variance of the Z_i are zero and one respectively, for all the values of i . Standardization tends to increase the influence of the variables whose variance is small and reduce the influence of variables whose variance is large. Furthermore the standardization procedure eliminates the influence of different measurement units over the analysis.

In the second step of factor analysis, the correlation coefficients are evaluated and presented in a matrix format¹³. Factor analysis takes data contained in this correlation matrix rearranges them in a manner that better explains the structure of the underlying system which produced the data. Therefore the correlation coefficient measures how well the variance of each constituent can be explained by relations with each other. The correlation coefficient is given as :

$$R_{xy} = \frac{(x - x_m)(y - y_m)}{[(x - x_m)]^2[(y - y_m)]^2}$$

In this expression, the correlation coefficients ($R_{x,y}$) are simply the sum (over all samples) of the products of the deviations of the x -measurements and the y -measurements on each sample, from the mean values of x and y respectively, for the complete set of samples¹⁴.

Table 3 presents the correlation matrix for the ground water quality data obtained from 15 samples around MSW dumpsite. In other words Factor Analysis is a multivariate statistical method that yields the general relationship between measured variables by showing multivariate patterns that may help to classify the original data. Elements belonging to a given factor were defined by factor matrix after varimax rotation, with those having strong correlations grouped into factors. The distribution manner of individual association of elements was determined by principal component method. Based on eigen values and varimax rotation three factors explained most of the variability. Multivariate statistical method was carried out by using IBM SPSS 20 Software.

Results and discussion

The analytical results of physico-chemical parameter of ground water around the municipal solid waste dumpsite is given in Table 1, main descriptive statistics for ground-water samples is given in Table 2. Statistical treatment of this data indicates their association and grouping with three factors shown in Table 3. The values were compared with Bureau of Indian Standard.

Statistical treatment of the ground water data indicates their association and grouping with three factors. pH of the ground water varies from 7.08 to 7.80 with an average of 7.46. All the water samples show neutral to

slightly basic values. pH does not show significant positive correlation with any parameter while it shows negative correlation with Cd, Cu, Na, Zn, Cu, Ni.

Factor analysis :

Factor-1, 2 and 3 :

Factor-1 exhibits 37.6% of the total variance of 65.4% with positive loading on B, Ba, Be, Ca, Cd, Cl, Co, Cu, Be, Fe, HCO₃, Li, Mg, Mn, Na, Sr, TDS, Zn ($r = 0.546$ to 0.883). Factor-2 exhibits 17.8% of the total variance of 65.4% with positive loading on Cl, Na, SO₄

and TDS ($r = 0.527$ to 0.923). Factor-3 exhibits 10.1% of the total variance of 65.4% with positive loading on CO₃ and Cr (0.635 and 0.512). The minimum and maximum concentration of these parameters along with their average values is listed in Table 2. These factors are attributed to anthropogenic influence of these parameters in groundwater. The data reveal that these parameters have migrated from dumpsite leachate. Sample nos. S₂, S₃, S₄, S₁₁, S₁₂, S₁₃ and S₁₅, show abnormal values with respect to its average and are either located very near to

Table 1

Sample	pH	EC (m.Sm)	TDS (ppm)	CO ₃ (ppm)	HCO ₃ (ppm)	Cl (ppm)	F (ppm)	NO ₃ (ppm)	SO ₄ (ppm)	Ca (ppm)	Mg (ppm)	Na (ppm)	K (ppm)	Fe (ppb)	
S1	7.08	1.1	700	24	198	130.8	0.5	51	98.5	98.5	63.6	1.6	544.5	544.5	
S2	7.44	1.7	1000	32	325	191.1	2.01	15.25	151.8	67.8	71	1.8	702.8	702.8	
S3	7.37	2	1280	34	180	195.2	0.8	109.8	161.1	64.6	106.6	2	692.7	692.7	
S4	7.22	1.4	905	20.3	300	149	1.8	69.1	128	67.4	68.2	1.9	618.7	618.7	
S5	7.6	1.12	720	10.2	180	120	1	80.2	95	45	68	1.8	514.1	514.14	
S6	7.64	1.12	710	12.2	175	150	0.52	70.2	100	42	72	1.9	495.9	495.9	
S7	7.75	1.36	830	35	258.9	130	1.6	60.2	100	62	75	2.4	480.6	480.62	
S8	7.59	0.9	500	38	140	105.6	0.53	48	60	30	48	1.8	483.7	483.71	
S9	7.14	0.75	480	28	140	80.2	0.94	62.1	78	20	35	0.7	450.2	450.2	
S10	7.24	2	1150	28	247	350	0.78	112.2	120	68	120	2.98	519.3	519.3	
S11	7.75	1.71	1000	30	192	226	2.1	115.8	126	50	78	38	611	611	
S12	7.43	2.11	1350	27	258	458.2	3.3	130.4	120	82.2	130	1.8	656.1	656.1	
S13	7.68	1.32	820	38	110.4	130	2.8	120.6	98.2	38.1	97	2	613.2	613.23	
S14	7.8	0.98	620	28	253	58	1.3	53.8	78	50	33	1.2	644.7	644.71	
S15	7.22	1.9	1200	12.6	240.2	262	1.2	120.9	190	70.2	100	8.2	651.2	651.22	
Sample	Li (ppb)	Be (ppb)	B (ppb)	Cr (ppb)	Mn (ppb)	Cd (ppb)	Ni (ppb)	Ba (ppb)	Pb (ppb)	Co (ppb)	Cu (ppb)	Zn (ppb)	As (ppb)	Se (ppb)	Sr (ppb)
S1	17.59	0.25	825.7	0.0872	23.88	0.063	0.118	128.6	0.0668	0.357	0.294	140.2	1.48	10.72	1231.9
S2	18.23	0.902	1523.2	12.55	90.21	4.081	7.831	290.5	3.183	1.327	132	4280.5	1.402	19.71	1852.31
S3	11.84	0.8	1476	16.52	39.1	0.027	0.1	154	0.53	0.306	3.321	2277	1.358	1034	1629.5
S4	12.49	0.63	799.8	10.26	29.45	0.032	0.096	148.9	5.331	0.275	144	44.82	1.257	9.94	1434.6
S5	7.52	0.09	324.2	10	11.45	0.037	4.553	44.21	0.67	0.432	0.801	55.71	7.89	8.27	603.33
S6	8.91	0.13	400.14	1.124	0.627	0.013	4.826	40.32	0.39	0.339	0.392	43.21	0.738	7.327	891.17
S7	5.23	0.04	300.13	2.723	0.77	0.049	3.89	73.41	0.29	0.513	4.236	33.73	0.923	8.021	1430.4
S8	5.69	0.02	334.7	1.727	0.413	0.042	4.103	68.23	0.35	0.382	0.382	40.203	0.831	7.172	680.34
S9	6.12	0.032	320.89	1.372	0.518	0.312	3.912	60.12	0.82	0.331	17.56	18.23	0.791	7.28	600.23
S10	6.33	0.08	450.2	8.021	0.823	0.051	6.13	60.32	0.193	0.892	6.021	100.23	2.021	12.95	1620.09
S11	14.18	0.04	885.8	22.934	15.5	0.014	0.118	107.8	0.869	0.325	5.649	334.7	1.438	12.7	1072.4
S12	24.07	0.04	831.6	9.556	30.6	0.07	0.116	112.8	1.1	0.377	6.787	85.5	1.61	18.62	2058.5
S13	10.91	0.07	750.21	8.234	0.517	0.09	3.981	57.23	0.319	0.437	3.823	104.14	0.812	9.612	950.21
S14	12.32	0.04	823.24	19.023	28.113	0.032	3.821	100.8	0.412	0.291	2.021	400.8	0.943	7.138	790.91
S15	15.21	0.08	890.7	9.047	70.12	0.0813	9.129	172.5	0.937	1.801	55.12	120.3	3.103	9.12	1860.21

Table 2

	Mean	Med	Min	Max		Mean	Med	Min	Max
pH	7.4633333	7.44	7.08	7.8	Be	0.2162667	0.155	0.02	0.902
EC	1.4313333	1.36	0.75	2.11	B	729.10067	799.8	300.13	1523.2
TDS	884.33333	830	480	1350	Cr	8.8785447	9.047	0.08717	22.934
CO ₃	26.486667	28	10.2	38	Mn	22.806067	15.5	0.413	90.21
HCO ₃	213.16667	198	110.4	325	Cd	0.3329533	0.049	0.013	4.081
Cl	182.40667	149	58	458.2	Ni	3.51488	3.912	0.0956	9.129
F	1.412	1.2	0.5	3.3	Ba	107.98213	100.81	40.32	290.47
NO ₃	81.302667	70.2	15.25	130.42	Pb	1.0307187	0.53	0.06678	5.331
SO ₄	81.302667	70.2	60	190	Co	0.559	0.377	0.275	1.801
Ca	113.64	100	20	98.5	Cu	25.492553	4.236	0.2943	143.98
Mg	57.053333	62	33	130	Zn	538.61953	100.23	18.23	4280.52
Na	77.693333	72	0.7	38	As	1.7731133	1.358	0.738	7.89
K	4.672	1.9	450.2	702.8	Se	78.838667	9.612	7.138	1034
Fe	578.58867	611	450.2	702.8	Sr	1247.0733	1231.9	600.23	2058.5
Li	11.776	11.84	5.23	24.07					

municipal dumpsite or at lower elevation with respect to dumpsite. The electrical conductivity of the samples were also in accordance with TDS values, indicating that the major cations like Na, Ca, Mg and major anion Cl⁻, HCO₃⁻, CO₃²⁻, SO₄²⁻ are present in considerable amounts. The sodium concentration in all the samples is within the permissible limit (200 mg/L) as per BIS. The sample S₃ and S₁₂ showed the highest value of Na, indicating their anthropogenic source. Except S₈ all the samples have high value of calcium which is above the permissible limit (75 mg/L) as per BIS. The mean value of calcium is 113.64, which may be due to geogenic sources. The reason may be due to the fact that calcium and magnesium present in many rocks and they come in contact with the groundwater table (National Research Council, Washington). Highest value of Ca is for S₁₅, S₃ and S₂ this may be due to their close proximity from dumpsite. Factor-1 showed the high positive loading on Ca and Mg (0.867 and 0.831) indicating the anthropogenic source also.

Sulphate is found to be in the range of 48 to 120.5 mg/L. All the samples are within the permissible limits (150 mg/L) as per BIS the highest value for sulphate is found in S₁₂ and S₁₃ as they are at the lower topographical elevation with respect to dumpsite. Factor-2 showed high positive loading of 0.923 on SO₄²⁻. Factor-1 and Factor-2 showed positive loading on chloride (0.490 and 0.597). The samples S₁₀, S₁₂ and S₁₅ showed the highest

value of chloride which exceeds the limit 250 mg/L as per BIS. All these samples are near and at lower elevation with respect to dumpsite. Factor-1 showed positive loading on HCO₃ (0.668) and Factor-2 showed positive loading on CO₃²⁻. S₂ and S₄ showed highest value for HCO₃ which are very near to dumpsite. If the metals are considered the Factor-1 shows 37.6% of the total variance of 65.4% with positive loading on B, Ba, Be, Cd, Co, Cu, Fe, Li, Mn, Sr, Zn. Factor-3 showed positive loading on Cr (0.512). Almost all the metals are within the permissible limit as per BIS. The minimum and maximum concentrations of these metals along with their average values are listed in Table 2 is attributed to anthropogenic influence as these metals have migrated from the dumpsite. Samples S₂, S₃ show abnormal values with respect to its average as they are located near to the dumpsite. Especially with reference to Cu, Fe and Zn, very abnormal average concentrations of Cu (25.49 ppb), Fe (578.59 ppb) and Zn (538.62 ppb) can be attributed to anthropogenic source. The MSW leachate contains heavy metals like Cd, Cr, Cu, Pb and Zn. Other metals like lithium and cobalt which are of secondary importance due to their low concentration are also present¹⁵. Arsenic is found to be in the range of 0.738 to 7.89 ppb which is within the permissible limit of 10 ppb as per BIS. Factor-2 showed a very low positive loading on arsenic. But S₅ showed high value of 7.89 ppb of arsenic. There are

Table 3

Variable	Factor	Communality	Eigen value	% Variance	Cum variance %	1	2	3
As	1	0.6013	10.8941	37.6	37.6	-0.011	0.143	-0.448
B	2	0.9769	5.1583	17.8	55.4	0.841	-0.219	0.374
Ba	3	0.9674	2.9183	10.1	65.4	0.847	-0.475	0.026
Be	4	0.9538	2.3147	8	73.4	0.666	-0.449	0.184
Ca	5	0.9279	1.7680	6.1	79.5	0.867	0.184	-0.212
Cd	6	0.9259	1.6960	5.8	85.3	0.546	-0.740	-0.057
Cl	7	0.8976	1.1393	3.9	89.3	0.590	0.597	-0.176
Co	8	0.9073	0.9001	3.1	92.4	0.561	-0.146	-0.645
CO ₃	9	0.8582	0.7891	2.7	95.1	0.013	-0.132	0.635
Cr	10	0.8975	0.6688	2.3	97.4	0.492	0.120	0.512
Cu	11	0.9331	0.3339	1.2	98.6	0.567	-0.730	-0.047
EC	12	0.9690	0.2425	0.8	99.4	0.829	0.495	-0.027
F	13	0.7686	0.0953	0.3	99.7	0.433	0.242	0.325
Fe	14	0.8757	0.0817	0.3	100	0.854	-0.006	0.323
HCO ₃	15	0.8001		0	100	0.668	-0.224	-0.213
K	16	0.6234		0	100	0.109	0.265	0.345
Li	17	0.9060		0	100	0.693	0.053	0.164
Mg	18	0.9101		0	100	0.831	0.315	-0.142
Mn	19	0.9457		0	100	0.849	-0.372	-0.144
Na	20	0.9291		0	100	0.581	0.695	-0.118
Ni	21	0.9301		0	100	0.083	-0.325	-0.694
NO ₃	22	0.8918		0	100	0.292	0.478	-0.162
Pb	23	0.8681		0	100	0.471	-0.325	-0.018
PH	24	0.8383		0	100	-0.242	0.005	0.425
Se	25	0.9496		0	100	0.327	0.165	0.407
SO ₄	26	0.9313		0	100	0.204	0.923	0.045
Sr	27	0.9656		0	100	0.883	0.226	-0.168
TDS	28	0.9893		0	100	0.835	0.527	-0.026
Zn	29	0.9497		0	100	0.677	-0.588	0.195

many possible routes of human exposure to arsenic from both natural and anthropogenic sources, although it primarily exists as arsenopyrite and as a constituent in several other sulfide minerals. The introduction of arsenic into ground water can occur as a result of its natural geological presence in local bedrock¹⁶. Arsenic-containing bedrock formations of this sort are not known in the present area of study.

Anthropogenic sources of arsenic are arsenic containing pesticides, agricultural products, textile chemicals, tanning agents of leather, anti-corrosive agents, glass and ceramic products and paints are known to have contain arsenic. Arsenic is used as arsenic pentoxide in wood preservative agents and found as a side product in sulphuric

acid production. In plastics, arsenic is used as an antibacterial additive as phenoxarsine oxide and 10,10'-bis(phenoxyarsinyl)oxide¹⁷. All the above sources of arsenic are found to be a part of MSW. Some arsenic contamination results from leaching from old waste dumps or from past use of arsenic containing pesticides¹⁸.

The metals Cu, Fe and Zn are characterized as undesirable metals in drinking water¹⁹. The heavy metals may be adsorbed by the soil strata or by the organic matter in soil. Heavy metals remain in the waste or at the waste-rock interface as a result of redox controlled precipitation reactions²⁰. Further the metal mobility is also controlled by physical sorptive mechanisms and landfills have an

inherent *in situ* capacity for minimizing the mobility of toxic heavy metals²¹.

Conclusions :

The present study of groundwater pollution due to MSW dumpsite in Autonagar area and the results of factors analysis performed identified three factors for groundwater controlling their variability. The migration of leachates from the dumpsite has found its way to the groundwater. The study reveals that the ground water parameters near the dumpsite are polluted compared to the samples collected far from dumpsite. The groundwater is polluted but to a lesser extent; this may be due to the stoppage of dumping of garbage and also excavations of the waste in vertical layers from the garbage cliff. The ultimate conclusion of this study is that the extent of pollution particularly heavy metals is not at major concern. The reason may be due the excavation of solid waste by the authorities in the year 2007 and the dumping of waste is stopped way back in the year 2005. Therefore there is no fresh leachate to percolate in the soil to further pollute the ground water.

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